

Carbon smart forestry under climate change

D5.3 Proceedings of the international and interdisciplinary conference

CARE4C in Forests: carbon balance, exchange, networking, linking disciplines – shaping research ideas

LEADING PARTICIPANT FBZ

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AUTHORS | Thilo Wagner ▪ Thilo.Wagner@wald-und-holz.nrw.de | Filippo Guerra ▪ filippo.guerra@wald-und-holz.nrw.de | Julia Schmucker ▪ julia.schmucker@tum.de | Enno Uhl ▪ enno.uhl@tum.de

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1. Introduction

CARE4C, *Carbon smart forestry under climate change*, aimed at creating knowledge about the relevance of carbon in forests and in forestry to contribute to a low carbon emitting society by utilizing the *Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions* funding instrument RISE (Research and Innovation Staff Exchange) Tasks and related secondments deal with a multitude of topics related to carbon issues in forestry and serve knowledge transfer and capacity building to foster expertise of young and experienced staff members in the field of adaptation and mitigation aspects in the frame of climate change.

2. Objectives

The international and interdisciplinary conference constitutes the main dissemination event within the project. The event aims at summarising the main outcomes of CARE4C, presenting the results to a broader audience and at developing strategies for future research.

3. Executive summary

CARE4C explores carbon sequestration in forests with an unprecedented level of comprehensiveness. This is achieved through empirical studies, statistical analyses along climate and management gradients, as well as integrated modelling and scenario analyses. With these new insights, a connection has been made from the response to drought stress on the cellular-level to forest structure at the landscape level. Particularly innovative and successful is the inclusion of CO₂ emissions resulting from forest management practices.

The fuel consumption and associated carbon dioxide emissions were thoroughly examined across different logging methods in various forest types. The results clearly demonstrate that the carbon sequestration through tree growth far exceeds the CO₂ emissions from forestry machinery many times over. The positive impact of active forest management on growth and the resulting higher carbon sequestration is therefore hardly diminished by harvesting machinery.

The first version of a widely applicable model for quantifying carbon balance in forest management at the landscape scale has been developed within the framework of CARE4C. The model will soon be available as open-source software (R package on CRAN). It will be applied in a comprehensive study where relevant case studies from all CARE4C partners, ranging from Poland to South Africa, will be integrated to provide a holistic view. Scenario analyses using this model will offer practical insights into the carbon balance at both local and regional levels. Planned model expansions include long-term carbon sequestration in wood products.

The excursion conducted during the conference vividly illustrated that large-scale climate-related damages will continue to be an inherent aspect of forest management. The urgency of projects like CARE4C, which analyse the consequences of such damages, develop counteractive measures, and facilitate the practical transfer of results, became all too apparent.

Conference participants agree that the CARE4C project has significantly contributed to a better understanding of carbon flows in forests under different forest management practices and stressors. Concepts for continuing research and development work have been jointly

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developed, with particular consideration given to aspects such as soil carbon dynamics, the long-term carbon sequestration potential in wood products, risk analysis in the face of increasing climate-related calamities, as well as the interrelationships between optimizing the carbon balance and other forest functions and ecosystem services.

4. Contributions

Summary of CARE4C: Idea, Objectives, Methods, Funding instrument, and Results

Enno Uhl¹

¹*Technical University of Munich (Germany)*

The presentation gives an overview about the frame of CARE4C from the starting point to project finalisation. The motivation for the project was driven by the perceptions that (i) forestry needs to contribute to a low carbon emitting society; (ii) we need to know how to improve carbon sinks and sources of forests and in forestry; (iii) we have to strive to develop carbon smart forest management for different forest types and climates to adapt to and mitigate climate change; and (iv) we need to promote capacity building for climate-smart forest management. We followed the objectives to (i) analyse, quantify and model the carbon sink resulting from forest growth and the carbon source by forest operations and risks; (ii) combine the sink and source aspects to an integrated picture and balance of the whole; (iii) publish and teach our results and new concept of a carbon smart forestry to enhance knowledge and skills at individual and organizational level; and finally to disseminate achievements and communicate the project to forest science, forest practice, general public and policy makers to foster a lower carbon emitting society.

Using a multi-gradient approach our research analysed different forest types at different scales along a climate and management gradient.

We received funding from the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action Staff and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) mainly promoting capacity building and cooperation through international and intersectoral mobility.

Nine academic and ten non-academic partners coming from Germany, Italy, Poland, South Africa, Switzerland, Spain, and Vietnam formed the consortium. In total, 74 different staff members have been seconded for 140 person months, thereof 29 early stage researchers, 38 experienced researchers and seven technical staff members.

WP2: Forest dynamics of carbon sequestration under climate change

Summary of work package 2: Forest dynamics of carbon sequestration under climate change

Miren del Rio¹

¹*Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria, Madrid (Spain)*

CARE4C WP2 aims to enhance knowledge for quantification and optimization of carbon storage dynamics by analyzing forest productivity and responses to climate change, depending on climate zone and forest management. In this presentation we summarize the main activities and results by tasks, and report on data generated and methods developed during the project, which could be the base for future common research.

Research activities on Task 2.1 “Physiological and morphological responses of trees to climate change” focused on: *Pinus sylvestris* growth response to climate along a climate gradient in Europe. Several traits (ring width, wood density, water use efficiency) were analyzed based on tree ring samples from pure and mixed stands. Results indicate a better response to drought in mixed stands. Other activities explored the effect of weather, water supply in other.

Research activities on Task 2.2 “Within tree partitioning and allometry shift under climate change addressed the following topics: i) Biometry and allometry of monumental trees in the Białowieża Strict Reserve; ii) Tree allometry in mixed vs monospecific stands along an environmental gradient. Results indicate significant changes in tree allometry between mixed and pure stands, with better canopy use in mixed stands; iii) Influence of social status on *Pinus radiata* tree growth and allometry; iv) Climate driven shifts in tree growth in beech in pure and multi species, multi layered stands, where positive trends modulated by elevation and composition were found.

Research activities on Task 2.3 “Resource partitioning between trees in a stand under climate change” focused on: i) Tree growth resilience to drought events. Trees from different mixed and monospecific stands along a climate gradient were analyzed, showing an overall better resistance and resilience in mixed than pure stands. ii) A review on tree growth partitioning within stand was done, highlighting the changes in partitioning with water supply (more homogeneous partitioning under drier conditions) and the relevance at stand level. iii) Other stresses like acid rain was analyzed. iv) long term mortality was quantified in terms of volume for several species along an environmental gradient, indicating that 30-40% of the total volume production was lost by mortality, which has important implications in terms of carbon sequestration. v) Tree growth response to silvicultural treatments under different climate was examined, including studies on *Pinus halepensis*, pure and mixed pine-oak stands and multi-species, multi-layered stands.

All research activities in WP2 generated valuable data datasets: mono and mixed pine-oak stands data (inventory data, intra-annual growth data, wood density and isotopes), data from thinning experiments in pine plantations, tree ring chronologies of Afrotropical forests, mortality data from long term plots in Europe, experimental plots in pine forest with different layers, Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TLS) data. Moreover, the research activities allowed us several methodological advances related to estimation of physiological and morphological traits, to TLS data use including the use of artificial intelligence methods, to carbon soil

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estimation and to modelling approaches. Moreover, new concepts for management of complex forest stands were developed.

Scots pine wood anatomy under different climate conditions in monospecific and mixed stands

Giulia Silvia Giberti¹

¹*Free University of Bozen/Bolzano (Italy)*

Forests are threatened by the increasingly severe and more frequent drought events worldwide. Given the recent drought-induced dieback of *P. sylvestris* at the southern edge of its distribution and the uncertainties related to the adaptability of *P. sylvestris* to future climatic conditions, the admixture between *P. sylvestris* and *Quercus* sp. has been investigated recently. The different ecology that characterizes these species could allow for interspecific facilitation mechanism to occur, providing ameliorated performances to *P. sylvestris*, especially during stressful events as droughts. With this regard, the most employed parameters to evaluate tree performances in different admixture were growth measures and dendrochronological records. Very little research has been done on wood anatomical traits in this context. In this study, we assess the role of tree admixture on *Pinus sylvestris* L. xylem traits in response to climatic variability like temperature and precipitation as well as extreme drought events. Monoculture and mixed stands of *P. sylvestris* and *Quercus* sp. were identified in Poland (6 plots) and Spain (6 plots), representing Continental and Mediterranean climate types, respectively. The results from two study locations highlighted that inter-specific facilitation mechanisms were detected in the admixture for *P. sylvestris* in both sites, especially in the first part of the growing season and during stressful events such as spring droughts, while they had negligible effects in the late growing season. Our findings suggested that this admixture could represent a practical silvicultural option for the adaptive management of *P. sylvestris* stands in the next decades.

Crown measurements in mono-specific and mixed stands using TSL

Felipe Bravo¹

¹*Universidad de Valladolid (Spain)*

Tree allometry and biomass allocation are driven by differential specific interactions (ie, intra- and inter-specific competition) modulating ecosystem services provision. This differential allometry can be study by detailed crown metrics obtained from Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS) point clouds processed with specific software. Outcomes can be discussed on the light of the optimal partitioning theory (OPT) and the allometric partitioning theory (APT). Mixed forests shown higher resilience and resistance than pure forests. Tree crowns show the effects of interaction between species. However, our understanding of how crown morphology changes due to density, competition, and mixture of species is limited. In this presentation, we insight on terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) to examine four crown variables (Maximum Crown Width Height, Crown Base Height, Crown Volume, and Crown Projection Area) in six permanent plots in Northern Spain. The plots contained two common European species: Scots pine and sessile oak. We scanned 193 pines and 256 oaks and conducted correlation tests and select eleven tree-level independent variables categorized into size, density, competition,

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and mixture. Multiple linear and non-linear regressions were used to fit models to the crown variables (Maximum Crown Width Height, Crown Base Height, Crown Volume and Crown Projection Area). The best models were selected based on the variable significance and biological meaning and lowest AIC Index. Our results show that pines have higher Maximum Crown Width Height and Crown Base Height than oaks but lower Crown Volume and Crown Projection Area. This complementarity between pines and oaks in mixtures can increase above ground structural diversity leading to overyielding (see Uzquiano et al, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13234955> for details) Besides that, TLS data extraction pipeline were presented including (i) tree isolation, (ii) crown segmentation, (iii) crown voxelization and (iv) crown metrics. Finally, tree interaction metrics based distances, influenced by each neighbor and crown overlapping and intermingling were highlighted as relevant for the analysis purposes.

The Impact of Climate and Adaptive Forest Management on the Intra-Annual Growth of *Pinus halepensis* Based on Long-Term Dendrometer Recordings

Jorge Olivar¹

¹*Agresta (Spain)*

Abstract: Projected climate changes for the Mediterranean region indicate prolonged periods of drought and an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events. Adjusting the density of forest stands through silvicultural methods can mitigate the impact of climate change on tree growth by improving the availability of soil water. We conducted an analysis on the growth patterns of *Pinus halepensis*, specifically focusing on the days of the year when 25%, 50%, and 75% of the annual basal growth occurred. Our study considered two different social statuses of the trees (suppressed and dominant) and evaluated four thinning intensities (15%, 30%, and 45% removal of basal area) over an 8-year period. The data collected through biweekly band dendrometer recordings revealed significant correlations between the timing of reaching 25% of the annual basal growth and the quantity of precipitation accumulated in the preceding winter. Conversely, the timing of reaching 75% of the annual basal growth was strongly influenced by shorter-term water availability, which also impacted the duration of the growing season. The modification of competition through thinning had a positive and significant impact on growth, resulting in a delayed attainment of 50% of the annual basal growth. These findings provide valuable insights into forest dynamics, aiding forest managers in making informed decisions when faced with water scarcity in forested areas

WP3: Carbon emission and risk strategies in forest management under climate change

Summary of work package 3: Carbon emission and risk strategies in forest management under climate change

Stefano Grigolato¹

¹*University of Padova (Italy)*

The WP3 Carbon emission and risk strategies in forest management under climate change was developed in three Tasks. The Task 3.1 is relating to the evaluation of the eco-efficiency of forestry machinery and forestry operations, with direct and indirect effects on carbon dioxide emissions and on the evaluation of practices also in relation to the release of post-harvest residues. Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 has focused on risk calculation and risk management in the forest sector.

In the specific, the Task 3.1 Carbon footprint for the forest value chain (supervised by HAFL) has proposed the development of a standardized methodology and protocol for data acquisition and nomenclature to improve the accuracy and the precision of data collected on forest machine fuel consumption (supported by SU and UP). A part of the activity is related to programming and implemented the IFOS datalogger (supported by HAFL) with SU partners in South-Africa. A specific activity was the test of UNIPD on fuel metering in collaboration with FBZ. A Fleet Management System (commercial use) and Can-Bus datalogger (research purpose) have been tested also tested with SGGW and FNZ, while Spatial distribution and quantification of logging residues to add precision in carbon cycle accounting has been implemented by SU and UNIPD.

In the frame of the Task 3.2: Risk calculation, the effect of fires on pine and eucalyptus stands by applying Monte Carlo simulations was modelled. How fires effect financial indicators (payback period, soil rent) and also carbon sequestration based on when the fire takes place within the rotation time was analyzed and modelled. Again, in the frame of Task 3.3: Risk management, Growth data was collected to model the risk of stand failure due to fires to feed portfolio optimization. Based on economic information (e.g. payback period, soil expectation value) and socio-economic indicators (e.g. carbon sequestration, fertilizer used) a robust, multi-objective land use portfolio was developed. Including socio-economic indicators diversify portfolio composition, however, this effect is reduced when accounting for time preferences by discounting ecosystem services.

Perspectives in using machine data to optimize energy efficiency in forestry operations

Stefano Grigolato¹

¹*University of Padova (Italy)*

Energy efficiency delivers a number of environmental benefits. It notably reduces GHG emissions, both direct emissions from fossil fuel combustion or consumption, and indirect emissions reductions from other energy resources. In the case of forest operations, energy efficiency can drive to the reduction of the use of not-renewable energy resources and the reduction of GHG emissions as well the reduction of operation cost.

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In the frame of the CARE4C project, different activities focused on the collection of engine machine data based on machine manufacturing web-application as well by specific datalogger able to read J1939 heavy duty mac. Two case studies will be presented. the first with the aim of verifying the usefulness for evaluating the efficiency in terms of direct consumption and therefore of emissions of the current commercially available machine monitoring systems. The second case has the objective of verifying the usefulness of a system developed specifically for detailed analyses of fuel consumption (and carbon emission) and the possibility of correlating fuel consumption and GHG emission to independent variables and factors (such as terrain, type of route, weather-climatic conditions) .

From the first case study it is determined that the use of user-friendly and commercial systems is suitable for analyses on a daily scale or over a longer period. In the case of specifically developed data loggers, the achievable detail has a high accuracy with a reference to measurements at 1Hz.hine engine standards.

An overview of fuel efficiency and associated emissions in plantation forestry

Bruce Talbot, Zimbili Sibiya¹

¹*University of Stellenbosch (SUN) (South Africa)*

Plantation Forestry differs from much of the semi-natural managed forestry of Europe. The primary objective is to grow large volumes of timber at lowest cost. Biodiversity and Social constraints are typically dealt with in a landscape mosaic fashion rather than on one and the same piece of land, resulting in more intensive operations being carried out in production areas. This has implications for greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Studies reviewed in this work, as well as wider publications, show that operational emissions are generally lower in plantation forestry than in other forms of forest management. The main reasons for this are that operations are highly rationalized. Plantation stands are uniform and tree size is large enough to result in high productivity rates. Road networks are dense and extraction effort is lower. A rough estimate is that machines working in sawtimber regime plantations in South Africa have a long-term productivity close to double that of their counterparts in e.g. European and perhaps the more comparable boreal forests. In addition, plantations have often been established in easily accessible land with processing plants in close proximity, reducing emissions from harvesting and transport. Studies considered in this deliverable show that, with the use of cut-to-length (CTL) machinery, timber can be harvested and extracted to roadside at the expense of just under one liter of diesel per cubic meter (m³), or some 2.7 kg of CO₂. Finally, the high growth rate makes it economically feasible to invest in intensive site management practices, something that increases emissions in the short term but accelerates growth and shortens rotation lengths to a degree that can well justify the emissions. This presentation highlights some of these aspects through roughly worked examples of each.

Multi-criteria optimization of South African forestry-avocado land-use portfolios

Isabelle Jarisch¹

¹*Technical University of Munich (Germany)*

The Institute of forest management at TUM did a risk evaluation of South African forest and avocado stands. We studied pine (*Pinus elliottii*, *Pinus patula*), eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus grandis*, *Eucalyptus grandis* x *urophylla*) as well as dryland and irrigated Avocado orchards (*Persea americana*). Based on economic information like the payback period and soil expectation value, as well as socio-economic indicators like carbon sequestration and fertilizer use we modelled a robust, multi-objective land use portfolio. We found that including socio-economic indicators diversify portfolio composition, however, this effect is reduced when accounting for time preferences by discounting ecosystem services.

To cover risk assessments, we modelled the effect of fires on pine and eucalyptus stands by applying Monte Carlo simulations. We studied how fires effect financial indicators (payback period, soil rent), as also carbon sequestration based on when the fire takes place within the rotation time. Besides these natural hazards, we also included a bootstrapping approach accounting for price and exchange rate fluctuations. These risk-adjusted ecosystem service indicators furthermore served as input information for a robust, multi-objective land-use model. Here, we demonstrated how land-use diversification can reduce risks by combining forestry with avocado stands. We used the risk adjusted ecosystem service indicators to form uncertainty boxes, with the standard deviation representing the uncertainty term. By multiplying an uncertainty factor with the standard deviation of each indicator, we could account for varying risk profiles dependent on different groups of decision makers. We could show that increasing risk aversion lead to higher diversification within the land-use portfolio, including more land-use types with more balanced shares. Discounting of ecosystem services indicators reduced portfolio diversification as discounting reduces the impact of uncertain events in the far future. However, choosing an appropriate discount rate is also linked to uncertainty. By including a set of discount rates simultaneously we accounted for market and preference changes and could show an offsetting effect on diversification.

Jarisch, I.; Bödeker, K.; Bingham, L.R.; Friedrich, S.; Kindu, M.; Knoke, T. (2022): The influence of discounting ecosystem services in robust multi-objective optimization – An application to a forestry-avocado land-use portfolio. *Forest Policy and Economics* 141: 1-18. doi: 10.1016/j.forpol.2022.102761.

4.1 WP4: Integration, training and career development

WP 4. Integration, training and career development

Camilla Wellstein¹

¹*Free University of Bozen/Bolzano (Italy)*

The Workpackage 4 is dedicated to integration, training, and career development within the CARE4C project. Regarding the training and career development, the main goals were to train postgraduates for a future career by developing their research competences in forest dynamics, carbon sequestration, carbon emission as well as risk strategies in forest

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management under climate change. The goals for the integration refer to the integration of research results into models as tools for forest research and management including guidelines as well as to develop a multi-criterial optimization. Correspondingly, three tasks were addressed: Task 4.1 Training activities (career development), Task 4.2 Integration (model extension/combination, results and expertise) and Task 4.3 Multi criterial optimization (supply chain).

At the end of the project 9 PhD theses have been finalized within CARE4C. The PhD students and post-docs profited from the international supervision and collaboration opportunities. Students of our institutions were also trained in groups taking advantage to have insight into the ongoing research projects. For international scholars, workshops and trainings were held that dealt with the research frontiers of CARE4C topics. For all the project participants, the international experience and networking opportunities contributed to the career development of each single person. Moreover, we realized a knowledge transfer to regional and national forest administrations.

Reporting on the model extension and combination, we used our results and expertise to define data standards and compare model parameterizations for multiple models. This leads to a better integration of models and also discusses the integration of models into simulation platforms.

We also reached the goal of integration in form of a generic simulation model for assessing silvicultural concepts in terms of CO₂ uptake and emissions. This model will be available as an R-Package within the open-source R environment and will be open for plugging in any user-defined silvicultural concepts.

Integration of carbon sequestration and carbon emission in forest systems. A modelling approach

Peter Biber¹

¹*Technical University of Munich (Germany)*

In order to allow to compare the C sequestration by forest growth with the C-emissions caused by forest operations, a pragmatic simulation model was developed. Each silvicultural concept to be assessed with the model must be broken down into several subsequent stand development phases with typical properties in terms of growth and yield and forest operations. A given large area of any desired size must be initially split up into the sub-areas covered by each of the phases mentioned above. Thus, users can set up any desired initial situation between a full afforestation and a forest estate in equilibrium. After the initialization, the cycling of the phase-wise areas is simulated by numerical solution of a set of differential equations. Hereby, users can fine-tune the degree of blur in this propagation due to their specific requirements. Damaging events that lead to area losses and therefore break the otherwise perfect area cycling can happen anytime. All areas affected by such an event, are thrown back into the concept's initial phase. The occurrence of such events is simulated stochastically, the typical-exponential-like distribution of the event strengths is taken into account, and users can scale the average event strength in an intuitive way. Thus, at any point of time, the simulation model knows the (sub-) areas attributed to each stand development phase as well as the area flows due to normal temporal dynamics and damage events. This allows an easy upscaling of the given phase-wise-per-unit-area growth and yield information (e.g. standing volume, volume increment, harvest amounts, etc.) to the whole area. Especially the harvest amounts are the backbone for estimates of the C emissions due to forest operations (ongoing development in collaboration with Prof. Stefano Grigolato, University of Padova).

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Preliminary simulations (expectedly) suggest C-Emissions from forest operations being orders of magnitude smaller than C-sequestration; however, they also indicate considerable steering potential for minimizing these emissions.

The model is implemented as an R package, which will be made publicly and freely available on CRAN in near time. It will become the core tool of an overarching study, where each CARE4C partner can plug in, simulate, and assess their own most relevant silvicultural systems in terms of C-sequestration and C-emissions. These individual results will be bundled into an international comparison of CARE4C case studies.

4.2 Excursion: Reforestation in times of climate change

Forest firefighter unit from Ponsse

Thilo Wagner, Filippo Guerra, Thomas Späthe, Jonas Baranowski, Julius Gerling¹

¹*Wald und Holz NRW (Germany)*

Initial situation:

- Rapid global warming, increase in extreme weather events such as heat waves
- German Association of forest owners (AGDW): estimated total damage due to forest fires in Germany 2022 significantly more than 600 million Euros, with regard to health (fine dust), nature (climate), economy (tourism, timber industry, regeneration costs).
- North Rhine-Westphalia: Increase in forest fire risk in recent years, caused primarily by rising temperatures and declining precipitation in the warmer seasons. (700 fire events last year).

Problems with existing technology:

Fire trucks:

- Existing multifunctional vehicles of the fire brigade are not very suitable for forest fires in Germany
- Many forest roads can only be used with a small number of existing, all-terrain fire-fighting vehicles. Off-road use of the vehicles is hardly possible.
- With these vehicles, the amount of water that can be transported off-road is clearly limited due to the payload (on average 2000 to 4000 liters).

Danger for firefighters:

- Firefighters often have to lay long hose lines to reach the fire. The range of 10-15 m of a normal jet pipe used in forest fires makes it necessary to be dangerously close to the source of the fire.

Solution for effective forest fire fighting:

In case of a fire there may not be always a road nearby. Modern forestry machines such as forwarders (tractors) are the most effective way to access a forest fire area in difficult terrain.

Forest machines are the most effective way to access a forest fire area. Operations in difficult terrain come as second nature to them, and they have more than enough capacity in their hydraulic system for demanding condition. Normally, these forestry machines transport raw wood from the stand to the forest road. Operations with high payloads are a matter of course for these machines and they have more than enough capacity in their hydraulic systems for such demanding conditions.

Base machine requirements for forwarders:

The firefighting equipment needs a load space at least 2 760 mm wide, a sufficiently powerful hydraulic pump and three connections to machine hydraulics.

- Load space width: 2 760 mm
- Min. hydraulic flow: 100 l/min

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- Min. hydraulic pressure: 235 bar
- 12 ton class forwarder

Reasons for acquisition by the state NRW in the FBZ:

1. To ensure mobile forest fire fighting in inaccessible areas throughout NRW in cooperation with the fire brigade. Especially under the special operating conditions in the Arnsberg Forest (28,000 ha of closed forest area, nature park with large numbers of visitors, 3 municipalities).
2. Ensuring the training of specialized personnel in the context of forest fire prevention
3. Improving forest firefighting strategies in NRW through innovation and research
4. Optimal conditions for stationing at the FBZ (technology, maintenance, machine operation, educational mission)

Figure 1 Presentation of the Ponsse Fire Fighter unit

Innovative technology for planting / machine-based planting site drill

Thilo Wagner, Filippo Guerra, Lars Bittis, Andre Schwane, Jonas Baranowski ¹

¹Wald und Holz NRW (Germany)

Current situation for planting in North Rhine Westphalia

In 2007 Windstorm Kyrill (Region South Westphalia): 50,000 ha storm damaged forests, 16 million m³ of timber, mainly spruce (4 x sustainable annual harvest).

Storm Friederike, 18. January 2018: following years of drought with bark beetle infestation 130,000 ha damaged forest for regeneration 40 million m³ of timber. 10 % of our forest area in the state

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Because of the situation different reforestation techniques are tested (e.g. seeding with drones, hydro seeding).

Manual planting is standard but trained professionals to perform the planting are scarce. So, the quality and controlling for untrained staff must be improved.

Working conditions on the afforestation plots have changed the last years:

- The areas were not cleared of logging residues.
- Grassing and emerging accompanying vegetation make it difficult to expose the mineral soil.

Under these conditions, machine-supported planting techniques are useful alternatives to manual planting.

Machine based planting site drill from Schwanitz

- Range of use: large plants from 1.20 cm to 2.20 cm shoot length and extensive root system in uncleared areas, with difficult, skellet-rich soils
- Capacity: 80 -110 plants per productive hour

Figure 2 The Schwanitz planting site drill in combination with a forwarder

Combination of two tools:

Brushwood rake:

Very practical for clearing areas from raspberries, blackberries and bracken and preparing planting sites.

No need to drive over the area, as a crane can be used guided precisely.

Easy handling and transport, no assembly required, equipment can be changed in seconds
Rear side with straight scraper bar for levelling.

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Planting site drill:

Several advantages can be addressed from the use of this tool:

- Existing forestry machines can be used as drive units
- No time-consuming conversion work on the forestry machine
- Quick change between grapple, planting site drill and brushwood clearing rake
- Long reach when used on a forwarder
- Ergonomic procedure: Forestry workers are physically relieved
- Deep loosening of the soil
- Planting possible even in overgrown areas without extensive tillage
- Even large plants can be planted without problems and are given sufficient root space
- Depending on the lane spacing, a strip of pioneer tree species is created between the crane areas

Working method:

The aim is to create a deeply loosened planting site that is free from and free from obstructing vegetation. The planting team consists of the forestry machine, the machine operator and two planters. The forestry machine takes onto the planting area:

- Planting site drill
- Plants (in a container protecting them from evaporation and sun)
- Water reservoir (optional)
- Brushwood clearing rake (optional)

The planting area is cleared of brushwood at certain points. If the area is heavily overgrown with brambles, this carpet of brambles is removed with the brushwood clearing rake. Disturbing branches can be placed on the alley with the grapple.

The planting site drill is used to create planting sites by gripping the upper part of the planting site drill with the gripper and rotating it with the rotator. The drill is placed on the ground and rotated into the soil to a depth of approx. 40 cm.

Planter 1 pulls the loose soil out of the planting hole with a hoe.

Planter 2 places the plant in the planting hole, fills it up with soil and treads the loose soil down.

If necessary, the plant is watered. The planting hole has a maximum size of 40 x 40 x 40 cm.

Results:

The total cost calculation of the proposed working method (forwarder + 2 planters) and a preliminary expert performance assessment of approx. 100 plants per hour, results in a cost rate of approx. 2.20 € per plant.

Compared to the planting costs of 0.60 € per plant in a standard manual planting procedure for the focal assortments (30 – 50 cm; 50 – 80 cm) in coniferous and deciduous wood, the planting procedure with the planting site borer will, from our current assessment, drop significantly.

When using larger hardwood assortments (80-120 cm; 120-150 cm; 150+ cm), the planting method is more important in terms of quality, productivity and ergonomics. The difference in planting costs compared to pure hand planting is no longer as high and is compensated by the previously described advantages.

Innovative technology for selective motor manual tending of young stands

Thilo Wagner, Filippo Guerra, Martin Nolte¹

¹*Wald und Holz NRW (Germany)*

Consequences from Windstorm Kyrill 18.01.2007:

The largest natural disaster which struck North Rhine Westphalia, particularly the forestry sector:

- Wind speeded up to 200 km / h (for 10 hours duration)
- 25 million trees, only in NRW, could not withstand the power of the tornado
- 50,000 ha storm damaged forests

The wind storm forced a change of thinking and strategy. Not only logging operations and cost reduction in wood supply chain, but also the subjects planting and subsequently tending come more and more into practical focus. 8 years after the storm event we have to think about strategies for tending the young stands and about optimal future thinning concepts.

2015 /The silvicultural results of Kyrill:

- inhomogeneous and wide age range of stands
- species-rich young stands (birch, oak, rowan, Douglas fir, broom, common maple, larch willow, spruce)
- Enormous planting density (appr. 17,000 trees / ha)
- Wish: Close to nature forestry based on reduced human intervention
- 17,980 ha area of young stands with a need for tending.
- 14 million Euro expenditure for tending.

The silvicultural goals in the young stands were the regulation of species mixing proportions, reduction of stem numbers (schematic removal or by encircling individuals) and a negative selection of trees with bad quality.

There was a need for a tending method, which can be adapted on flexible silvicultural objectives and different thinning grades. Whereas established clearing saws were limited for this kind of application due to the cutting diameter, the Husqvarna 535 FBX Spacer turned out as a useful tool. Therefore, FBZ developed a complete working procedure with planning and assessment of quality with the least possible effort of tending operation using the spacer.

Calculation scheme for time requirement and costs of spacing:

Time requirement and costs		
Diameter remaining stand	23	mm
Number of removed trees	1,60	Thousand
Sloop	13	%
Non productive time (Supplement)	47	% of productive time
Time requirement	21,96	h/ha
Hourly earnings	18,00	€/h
Non wage labour cost	100	% hourly earnings
Wage costs	791	€/ha
Operating costs Spacer	12,00	€/h
Share of productive time	53	% total time
Material costs	139,67	€ / ha
Total cost	930,26	€/ha

New method of tending of young Douglas fir stands:

After the major windthrows events, many forest owners are uncertain about efficient management of young stands on afforested sites. With respect to Douglas fir, early tending of young stands leads to an improved performance of the stands.

So far, for the commonly used method, the tending process has been divided into several separate work steps using a handsaw (pruning of potential crop trees) and a chainsaw (removal of competing trees).

Step 1: Selection & pruning of future crop trees

Future crop trees are selected, pruned (using a cordless pruning shear) and permanently marked (also adjacent competing trees) by a qualified forest worker. The use of electrified pruning shears results in better pruning quality and faster occlusion of wounds.

Step 2: Removal of complete trees

In autumn, competing trees adjacent to future crop trees are removed, using a „Spacer“.

Figure 3 Practical use of the Stihl spacing saw powered with modern rechargeable battery

Waldinfo.NRW - the forest information portal for North Rhine-Westphalia

Alexander Weller¹

¹*Wald und Holz NRW (Germany)*

With a share of 63%, North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) has a comparatively high proportion of private forest. In addition, NRW is pursuing a consistent open data strategy. For this reason, Waldinfo.NRW was set up in 2018 as a central access point to selected, forest relevant open geodata. Waldinfo.NRW contains nine different map groups with over 40 different map themes, e.g. on forest ecology, forest functions, forest management or forest nature conservation. It also contains a variety of useful tools, for example to measure distances and areas, to draw points, lines, and polygons or to create a height profile. In addition to geodata, Waldinfo.NRW also offers access to many documents and concepts of the forest administration via the front page (www.waldinfo.nrw.de), such as the silviculture concept NRW. With its information, Waldinfo.NRW is currently making a major contribution to climate-adapted reforestation of the numerous calamity areas in North Rhine-Westphalia. The included forest site maps (to be found in the map group „Waldökologie“ / Forest Ecology) provide information about the water and nutrient supply as well as the growing season as an expression of the temperature, for current climate and for two climate scenarios. Much more important, the forest site map shows the tree species recommended for the respective forest site. The recommendations come from the silviculture concept NRW and always include mixed forest types. In summary: Waldinfo

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offers private forest owners free access to many forest-related open geodata and is a valuable support and advisory tool for forestry, especially for climate-adaptive reforestation.

The Silviculture and Reforestation Concept of North Rhine Westphalia – New Instruments for Forest Ownership

Heiner Heile¹

¹*Wald und Holz NRW*

In the context of the forest adaptation strategy, the state of North Rhine-Westphalia has developed a new Forestry Concept 2.0. This is a recommendation with many options for all types of forest property.

The forestry concept includes general forestry principles, specific types of forest development with site reference and mixtures of tree species, concrete forest management recommendations for forest stands as well as information on other aspects relevant to forest development. The recommendations for forest development support the current objectives for forest construction in North Rhine-Westphalia by developing site-appropriate and structured mixed stands from predominantly native tree species using suitable propagating material of regionally adapted origin.

Imported tree species are also recommended if scientific evidence is available and long-term cultivation experience in Germany is available. The forestry recommendations are particularly aimed at increasing the stability and resilience of forests to climate change, as well as at reducing the risks to forestry operations. The 72 forest site types of the concept derived for NRW are based on a combination of the location factors temperature, water availability and nutrient supply. The assignment for a specific forest stock is possible via the digitally available soil and location maps as well as current climate data and forecasts on the effects of climate change in NRW (see link: <https://www.waldinfo.nrw.de/>). The second pillar of the forest construction concept are the 23 forest development types (WET).

These are ideally typical mixed stocks suitable for the location, whose tree species composition as a target for the establishment of the stock or for the establishment of a tree species or stock transformation in climate change can be used. The participation of at least three to four tree species involved in the forest development type supports a long-term risk-minimized forest development for the forestry companies. Imported tree species are also recommended if scientific evidence is available and long-term cultivation experience in Germany is available. The forestry recommendations are particularly aimed at increasing the stability and resilience of forests to climate change, as well as at reducing the risks to forestry operations. The forest development types are described in the form of short profiles. They contain the respective information on the mission statement (structure) of the WET, on the site requirements (heat, water, nutrients) and provide information on the natural forest society and the environment like the possible forest habitat type. In addition, the forest functions (use, protection function and recreation) of the WET are presented and recommendations for forest ownership regarding the possible production target (e. g. logs, valuable wood, growth performance, climate protection), as well as the stock target (percentage of tree species).

At the heart of the forestry concept are the four overviews for the location allocation of forest development types. Here a selection of locally suitable forest development types is shown for certain site conditions.

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Climate protection and risk minimization in climate change can be operated with all the WETs assigned to the location in the concept. The WETs shown in bold are particularly recommended at the respective location type due to their forest growth potential. The light blue colored WETs in the overview are fully compatible with the FFH-Directive in the case of existing forest habitat types, while the dark blue colored WETs are subject to minor restrictions. The fourth most important and comprehensive module is the forest management recommendations. They show schematic measures that can be implemented in the long term by means of forest development types. The forest construction measures are oriented towards the leading main tree type, but also the accompanying tree species in the respective WET are taken into account. The basis is the typical forest development phases (young to mature and regenerative phases) and structural parameters of forest stocks (top of the stock). This is where the forest owners are supported by the concept and "picked up" in the current state of the respective forest management possibilities in its sustainable forest management decision-making. There is therefore no "sample solution" but always several options. Additional information on issues related to forest functions, the forest floor map NRW and the site requirements of forest tree species are presented in the appendix to the concept. In addition, overviews of the stocking and rejuvenation objectives of the WET, growth boards of selected tree species, and their dimensioning are included. Further background information on the forest construction concept is available for forest ownership at the State Forest and Timber Management North Rhine-Westphalia, forested planning advice and guidance as usual at the Regional Forestry.

Like a satellite, the Reforestation Concept of North Rhine Westphalia is technically and conceptually based on the Silviculture Concept of North Rhine Westphalia and complements it in the area of stand establishment on large open areas.

The presented planting schemes convey the basic idea of a mixed stand according to the "Four Tree Species Principle" to the forest owner. The corresponding key figures (plant numbers, costs, labor hours for the maintenance of the stands) enable the forest owners to make fact-based silvicultural decisions.

Competence Centre Forest and Timber 4.0 (KWH4.0) and its sensor networks

Frank Heinze¹

¹*Kompetenzzentrum Wald und Holz 4.0 (KWH4.0) (Germany)*

The Competence Centre Forest and Timber 4.0 (KWH4.0) further develops Industry 4.0 concepts to promote the digitalization of the forest and timber industry and to meet current challenges from ecology, economy, and climate change. In the KWH4.0, RIF Institute for Research and Transfer e. V. (Dortmund) cooperates with RWTH Aachen University with the Institute for Man-Machine Interaction (MMI), the Laboratory for Machine Tools and Production Engineering (WZL) and the Institute of Industrial Engineering and Ergonomics (IAW), as well as the Forestry Education Centre (FBZ) of the Centre for Forestry and Timber Industry of the State Enterprise Forestry and Timber NRW in Arnsberg. KWH4.0 maintains an industry working group consisting of almost 50 companies and associations. The majority consists of SMEs from the forest sector in North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany, representing all stages of the value chain.

KWH4.0 maintains the Smart Forest Labs. The Smart Forest Labs are key components for the practical implementation and testing of newly developed components, systems, and processes,

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for the evaluation of standards, and for the training of stakeholders. Examples of the real Smart Forest Lab include forest machines equipped with their corresponding Digital Twins. The Digital Twin provides the interconnection features to other Digital Twins, software services, and human-machine-interfaces.

Another example of the Smart Forest Labs is the sensor networks AJA that were built up by the Munich start-up foldAI. KWH4.0 operates a total of 20 sensor networks in different stands in the region Arnsberg. The sensor networks monitor microclimate, soil parameters, tree vibrations and growth, and biodiversity (based on acoustic data). The stands include young stands, as well as old stands, natural cells, as well as commercial stands. The tree types represent typical tree types of the region like sessile oak, European beech, spruce, birch, Douglas fir and giant live trees.

The monitoring data is e. g. used to derive information of the biodiversity of different stand types and of the health condition of the trees.

Figure 4 Outdoor presentation of the Competence Center forest and timber 4.0

4.3 Developing future research strategies

R&I actions and tools under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe

Michael Wolf¹

¹DG AGRI

As a flagship initiative of the European Green Deal and building on the 2030 biodiversity strategy, the Commission adopted the new EU forest strategy (EUFS) for 2030, covering the whole forest cycle and promoting the many services that forests provide.

It sets out a vision and concrete actions to improve the quantity and quality of EU forests and strengthen their protection, restoration and resilience. It aims to adapt Europe's forests to the new conditions, weather extremes and high uncertainty brought about by climate change. This is a precondition for forests to continue delivering their socio-economic functions, and to ensure vibrant rural areas with thriving populations.

It builds on best available scientific evidence and will be implemented in respect of subsidiarity and better regulation principles.

At the core of the EUFS are the economic, social and environmental functions of forests. A special focus lies on the multi-functional role of forests, the contribution of foresters and the entire forest-based value chain for achieving by 2050 a sustainable and climate-neutral economy. Furthermore, other main topics are the restoration, resilience and protection of forest ecosystems and an adequate forest monitoring and strategic planning for the future.

Enabling elements of the EUFS are a strong research and innovation agenda, an inclusive and coherent EU forest governance framework and the implementation and enforcement of existing EU acquis.

The task of research and innovation here is the enhancement of the knowledge on climate change impacts, the contribution to a greater diversity of forests and genetic resources, and to provide evidence-based and practically feasible guidance for climate change mitigation and adaptation in line with biodiversity objectives. Furthermore research should focus on how to add more value on sustainable and multifunctional forests to maximise the benefits for society (e.g. carbon farming, etc.), support the design and implementation of forest restoration strategies with engagement of the society and in different ecological and socio-economic settings, including through the mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' and to Improve the understanding of primary and old-growth forests and of their biodiversity and climate functions. Other important priorities include innovative and resource efficient bio-based products to substitute non-renewable materials, competitiveness of the forest-based sector and boosting rural economies by enhancing skills, knowledge and innovation. Also the development of a "Planning our Future Forests" research and innovation agenda together with Member States and stakeholders by jointly identifying research gaps and future priorities for forestry and the forest-based sector is an important task for the future. This all can be reached by the enhancement of EU cooperation by proposing a Research and Innovation partnership on forestry, including flagships for testing and demonstrating solutions on selected key strategic domains.

The Forest R&I under Horizon Europe (2021-2024) contains a budget of 140 million € in 22 projects. This is an increase of 50 % compared to Horizon 2020. The multi-actor approach is a requirement to enhance the participation of foresters from the beginning of the projects. Links

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to large-scale instruments, such as EU partnerships and missions, will be promoted. European key policies as the EUFS and CAP are supported.

In the Cluster 6 there are multiple forestry related topics included, which could be interesting for a CARE4C follow-up project. Potential R&I gaps are:

- Stronger focus on Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)
- Enabling a sustainable forest management under a changing climate (e.g. prevention and management of large-scale disturbances, forest/plant health, availability of suitable forest reproductive material, prestoration, etc.)
- Addressing trade-offs and synergies: how to ensure the development of the bioeconomy to substitute fossil-based material and at the same time increase the sink and reduce forest vulnerability to climate change?
- Digital innovations and new technologies (e.g. AI and remote sensing, new breeding techniques, etc.)
- Innovative wood-based products to substitute fossil-based counterparts - focus on construction/renovation (European Bauhaus)
- (International) governance
- Urban forestry
- Multi-actor approach

FOREST EUROPE's contribution to sustainable forest management in the era of challenges facing Europe's forest sector

Juliet Achieng¹, Bernhard Wolfslehner¹ and Thomas Haußmann¹

¹FOREST EUROPE Liaison Unit Bonn

FOREST EUROPE, formerly known as the Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe, is a pan-European high-level voluntary political process established to develop common strategies on how to protect and sustainably manage European forests while also promoting intergovernmental dialogue and cooperation. In so doing, FOREST EUROPE has developed the definition of sustainable forest management (SFM), criteria & indicators for SFM, and guidelines for SFM and afforestation and reforestation. FOREST EUROPE process consists of 45 European states and the European Union as signatories and 14 countries and 45 organizations as observers. The chairmanship rotates among the signatories. The current Liaison Unit is located in Bonn under the chairmanship of Germany with support from the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) in cooperation with the European Forest Institute (EFI). The Ministerial Conferences are FOREST EUROPE's biggest event organized after every 4-5 years at the end of a country's chairmanship and where decisions on issues of highest political and social relevance regarding forests and forestry are taken. So far there have been 8 of these events organized since 1990. The next conference will take place in Bonn, Germany in October 2024.

FOREST EUROPE develops a work programme for very chairmanship to ensure effective planning of activities with the current one running from 2021-2024. It comprises of three main focus areas, which are sustainable forest management (SFM), pan-European Forest Risk Knowledge Mechanism (FoRISK) and Green Jobs and Forest Education. The overarching topics are covered by the rapid response mechanism and communication. The topics covered by the current work programme are shaped by the new challenges that forestry in Europe is facing. At the moment we are confronted by rapid environmental changes which demand an extra-ordinary adaptation and response measures. Furthermore, society has different demands towards forestry while at the same time, the policy arena is turbulent with many new

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policies and policy priorities evolving within a very short time. The SFM concept that has been proposed as a solution for many years is no longer the leading principle, however it is still a major reference. There is need for investigating how it relates to other concepts, its strengths and weaknesses, how it can serve as a balancing tool to moderate new claims on forests and its resources and how to keep it fit for the future.

According to the State of Europe's Forest Report (2020), there has been increase in European forest area as well as protected forest area, and the carbon stock has been growing with sustainable harvest rates. The European forest-based sector plays a big economic role especially for the rural areas. Despite all the positives, forest ecosystems are still increasingly under pressure from climate change and natural disasters and there is a heated debate on biodiversity protection. The "best" future use of forests in a changing environment and a changing economic paradigm of a carbon-neutral society are also subject of controversy. Therefore, in the Bratislava Ministerial Declaration of 2021 the following points were re-emphasized as a way forward for Europe's forests: an early uptake of climate change in national forest policy debates, an uptake and update in national forest programmes, shaping and adjusting of national forest monitoring, promotion of a combined climate change adaptation and mitigation and fostering research and collaboration on adaptive forest management, including forest genetics. To keep SFM fit for the future, gaps in current policy developments need to be proactively addressed while keeping the backbone. It is important to find the unique selling point of European forestry and to promote it in a holistic approach. The tools and instruments of forestry should be further developed and a careful forest monitoring in the context of carbon and biodiversity has to be promoted. Making SFM more tangible to a broader audience through creating a new vision and narratives will enhance it as a sustainable concept in the future. This is possible through collaborations on forest-related topics.

Figure 5 Presentation of Forest Europe at the workshop session

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Workshop - Developing future research projects and funding opportunities

Melanie Schulte¹

¹*Bavarian Research Alliance (BayFOR) (Germany)*

The Bavarian Research Alliance GmbH (BayFOR) – with its Scientific Coordination Office Bavaria-Africa – participated as an external expert in the Care4C Final Conference, to take-up the project results and thereof facilitates the conference workshop on follow-up funding opportunities. BayFOR's ambition in this workshop was to provide comprehensive advisory services on EU research and innovation funding and supports the application process and look for suitable project partners. In this line, it had already supported the Care4C proposal and provided support in project implementation-related questions.

To initiate the discussion and brainstorming on a "Care4C 2.0" project, BayFOR presented different Horizon Europe topics and those of other related international initiatives. Especially Horizon Europe constitutes a suitable option for international collaboration, as in Care4C's case with South African and Vietnamese partners. In the programme, international collaboration builds one of the core goals, which is also enforced by the implementation of the Africa Initiative II. It explicitly includes EU-AU collaborate topics of about 300 million € for the 2023-2024 Work Programme in the fields of i.e. Green Transition, Public Health, Innovation and Technology and Capacities for Science, and thus aligns well with the objectives of Care4C and follow-up projects.

4.4 External statements towards future research

To include the experience and views of practitioners and researchers not included in CARE4C into the discussion about future research, experts from different countries and institutions were invited to give a statement.

Kevin Cianfaglione

Université Catholique de Lille, France

The main focus areas of future research could be:

- Forest ecosystem dynamics in past, present and future.
- Primary forests and not-managed forests. To understand natural processes and to guarantee the biodiversity, it is important as both those types of forests should be used as a template for the scientific studies and for the forest management. Following natural tendencies is more economic than working against them.
- The treatment and use of alien species. Invasive species are often too widely distributed to fight them back. A strategy for their use/management is urgently needed, not based on fear and hatred.

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Roberto Tognetti*Università degli Studi del Molise, Italy*

- There must be a discussion about the carbon storage due to different qualities and uses of timber (e.g. construction wood).
- Other effects in carbon sequestration, beside the storage in wood, have to be addressed. E.g. the albedo effect and other climatic effects of silvicultural management.
- The species composition in future forests and the use of the wood of those species has to be addressed.

Jaroslav Bator*Lasy Państwowe, Poland*

Main issues for future research are:

- the maximisation of carbon sequestration in forest management,
- the development and implementation of models to calculate the carbon footprints of state forest companies,
- the integration of the society expectation concerning forests, further ecological education and promotion of wood products,
- presence of the Polish State Forest as a non academic unit in further discussion and new projects.

Stefan Flückiger*BFH-HAFL, Switzerland*

- Carbon capture (first priority) and storage (only for limited time) in forests is still an important topic.
- It is very important to not only take into account the quantity of wood but first of all the quality of the stored carbon: is it suitable for long-term storage in the value chain?
- In research the choice of market- and nature suitable species, (shortener) production time, the vitality of the trees which remains the longest time in climate risk and soil fertility are the main topics for forest management

Mario Broll (represented by Camilla Wellstein)*Province of Bolzano, Italy*

Research and need for action about carbon:

- CO2 at the stock exchange

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- Carbon sequestration values
- Better consideration of growth processes and age (young forests, old growth forests)
- Selling of carbon storage of forests
- Inter-company level of ecosystem services (e.g., erosion protection in protection forests)
- Forest loss risk compensation (e.g., farmers' association)
- Need for insurance in case of disturbance events
- Economical calculations and insurance mathematics

Tomasz Kurek

Lasy Państwowe, Poland

- The future research on carbon sequestration should take into account the influence of wild game. Especially in forest regeneration it plays a big role and influences the general development of forests.
- The Polish state forest is open for cooperation and is willing to take part in future projects.

Martin Ziesak

BFH-HAFL, Switzerland

- Besides EU funding also national and bilateral funding possibilities should be considered
- Carbon labelling of products might be an issue in the future. However, transparent numbers for their (individual) calculation are still missing.
- There should be a precise and transparent monitoring for the calculation of CO₂ per wood unit to build up trust, transparency and reliability of the forest sector.

Andrés Bravo-Oviedo

The National Museum of Natural Sciences, Spain

- Back-to-Nature can be accomplished with a Back-to-Silviculture turn.
- Potential trade-offs between biodiversity and bioeconomy have to be taken into account.
- Important question: How can we move towards a strong sustainability paradigm?

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Mobility activities in the frame of CARE4C.